

Review

Phytotherapy in the Management of Low Back Pain: A Comparative Analysis with Conventional Pharmacological Interventions.

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Abstract

Background: Low back pain (LBP) is a leading cause of global disability, affecting up to 80% of the population. While conventional pharmacological treatments (NSAIDs, paracetamol) are standard, their efficacy is often limited by side effects or insufficient relief, particularly in chronic cases. Consequently, interest in Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) and phytotherapy has increased.

Objective: To evaluate the clinical benefits of phytotherapy in the treatment of LBP and compare its efficacy and safety with conventional pharmacological interventions.

Methods: A narrative literature review was conducted, focusing on clinical guidelines, comparative studies, and TCM theoretical frameworks. The review analysed the aetiopathogenesis of LBP, the structure of herbal formulations (Emperor, Minister, Assistant, Envoy), and the comparative outcomes of botanical vs. synthetic drugs.

Results: Evidence suggests that conventional analgesics, such as paracetamol, often show no superiority over placebo for acute non-specific LBP. In contrast, phytotherapeutic agents, specifically *Boswellia serrata*, *Curcuma longa*, and the *Du Huo Ji Sheng Tang* formula, demonstrated significant reductions in pain intensity and functional disability. Studies indicated that combining phytotherapy with acupuncture (e.g., *Palmijihwang-hwan*) provides superior cost-effectiveness and clinical outcomes compared to isolated conventional therapies.

Conclusion: Phytotherapy is a viable and safe complementary alternative for managing LBP. It addresses the systemic and energetic imbalances (such as Kidney Yang deficiency or Qi stagnation) that conventional medicine often overlooks. While further longitudinal trials are needed to standardise dosages, integrating herbal medicine into multidisciplinary care offers a promising path for reducing the global burden of LBP.

Keywords: Low back pain; Phytotherapy; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Pharmacology; Analgesia.

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1. Introduction

LBP, defined as pain located in the lower lumbar region, constitutes one of the most prevalent and disabling musculoskeletal problems worldwide, affecting up to 80% of the population at some point in their lives. The impact of this clinical condition is significant, appearing as the second most frequent cause of medical consultations, surpassed only by respiratory infections. The causes of LBP are varied, ranging from the overloading of lumbar spine structures, "comfortable" posture, sedentary lifestyles, trauma, ageing, and ergonomic factors. It can be classified as acute, subacute, or chronic depending on the duration of the pain ¹⁻³.

The physical examination involves checking posture, palpation of the lumbar spine (spinous processes, paravertebral muscles), assessment of range of motion, and specific tests such as: the Schober test, which measures lumbar mobility; sciatic nerve tension tests, including the Lasègue test (Straight Leg Raise), important in identifying radiculopathy; and neurological examination of the lower limbs (muscle strength, reflexes, sensitivity), performed even in the absence of radiating symptoms to detect neurological deficits^{18,19}.

When a diagnosis has not yet been established at this stage, it becomes urgent to resort to complementary exams, such as^{2,7}: plain X-rays, to assess bone changes in cases where fractures or deformities are suspected; Computed Tomography (CT) and Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), used when complications are suspected, symptoms persist, or warning signs are present, allowing for a detailed assessment of bone structures and soft tissues; and functional, non-invasive exams, such as cypholordometry, which can be used in postural assessment and monitoring evolution, particularly in rehabilitation cases²⁰.

Thus, the diagnosis, based on clinical guidelines and scientific evidence, ensures the identification of the main causes of LBP, guiding the subsequent steps, namely treatment. To guide the diagnosis, there are the Guidelines from the American College of Physicians and the American Pain Society for the diagnosis and treatment of LBP²¹⁻²⁵.

2.3. Conventional treatment

Conventional treatment for LBP may begin with the avoidance of activities that overload the spine and cause pain²⁶⁻²⁸. There are three types of treatment: non-pharmacological, pharmacological, and surgical.

In terms of pharmacological therapy, paracetamol is frequently recommended for pain relief, unless there is inflammation. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), whether over-the-counter or prescribed, can also relieve pain and simultaneously decrease inflammation^{29,30}.

When these options fail, opioid analgesics may be prescribed, but these should be used for a short period as they can increase pain sensitivity, cause side effects (e.g., drowsiness), confusion, and constipation, with a risk of developing a substance use disorder. It is also possible to use muscle relaxants; carisoprodol, cyclobenzaprine, diazepam, metaxalone, or methocarbamol are some of the medications used to reduce muscle spasms, though they are not suitable for the elderly³¹⁻³³.

Other forms of treatment may include the application of heat or cold, massage, and physiotherapy. In the case of chronic LBP, aerobic exercises can help. If analgesics are ineffective, other treatments may be considered, such as facet joint injections, epidural corticosteroid injections, and, in cases of herniated discs or severe spinal stenosis, surgery is recommended³⁴.

Therefore, pharmacological options include analgesics, NSAIDs, and muscle relaxants, while physiotherapy utilises resources such as kinesiotherapy, electrotherapy, thermotherapy, and manual techniques, each presenting a varying degree of scientific evidence for pain reduction and functional improvement^{35,36}.

Taking into account each type of LBP, as therapeutic options vary according to chronicity and severity, Lopes³⁷ explains that for the treatment of: subacute LBP, in addition to the non-pharmacological therapeutic plan (exercises and psychotherapy), there are 1st-line treatments, characterised by the administration of NSAIDs and paracetamol, and 2nd-line treatments, which involve the administration of non-benzodiazepine skeletal muscle relaxants; chronic LBP, movement exercises and other interventions are recommended, with 1st-line treatment including NSAIDs and paracetamol and 2nd-line treatment including serotonin-noradrenaline reuptake inhibitor (SNRI) antidepressants, tricyclic antidepressants, and tramadol.

3. Phytotherapy

3.1. Traditional Chinese Medicine

TCM is an ancient medical system originating in China, involving a series of external practices for the understanding, diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of diseases, based on the dynamic balance between *Yin* and *Yang* forces and the circulation of vital energy (*Qi*)^{38,39}.

It is a medical system that practices holistic medicine, evaluating the person as a whole (physically, psychically, and environmentally) and based on philosophical principles such as *Yin-Yang* (the duality of opposing forces that must be balanced to ensure health), the Five Elements (wood, fire, earth, metal, and water), Meridian Theory (energy channels), *Zang-Fu* (*Zang* organs, which are *Yin*, and *Fu* viscera, which are *Yang*), *Qi* and *Xue* (blood) organs, and diagnosis by Syndrome Differentiation^{39,40}. Thus, one agrees with Maciocia⁴¹ when he states that Chinese medicine diagnosis is also strong in its holistic view of body and mind. Probably no other form of diagnosis is capable of making such a comprehensive, holistic, and detailed assessment of a patient in a relatively short time, gathering all the different elements of the diagnosis.

3.2. Phytotherapy

While conventional medicine resorts to pharmacological therapy, phytotherapy resorts to plants. Oliveira⁴² explains that in Western medicine, drugs usually consist of an active principle, which are responsible for the therapeutic effect, and excipients, which serve as vehicles, helping in the transport and guidance of the active principle to the desired site of action. In Chinese phytotherapy, the situation is similar: herbal formulas follow an organised structure, and the main function is performed by the plant designated as the Emperor, the "heart" of the formula, corresponding to the active principle that acts on the main symptom⁴²⁻⁴⁴. The remaining plants in the formula are designated as Minister, Assistant, and Envoy, acting in a complementary manner:

- The Minister reinforces the main effect (the action of the Emperor) and treats secondary symptoms;
- The Assistant, or auxiliary plant, is responsible for reinforcing the action of the Emperor and Minister, reducing potential adverse effects or toxicity, and treating secondary symptoms;
- The Envoy, or guide plant, directs the action of the plants in the body (to the affected meridian, system, or part of the body), promoting harmony in the therapeutic action. It is important to note that each formula may contain one or more plants from each category.

Phytotherapy treats pathologies based on energetic patterns identified during diagnosis, governed by seven pillars⁴⁵: Proven clinical efficacy; Safety of use; Therapeutic individuality; Health promotion and disease prevention; Holistic approach; Sustainability and environmental respect; and Integration with other therapies.

Plant-drug interactions are a topic of great relevance, as they can enhance benefits or cause clinical risks, altering the absorption, metabolism, transport, and action of drugs. It is crucial that phytotherapy is performed by a phytotherapist, a TCM specialist, or a health professional with knowledge in the field. This is because there is the assumption that medicinal plants, as well as natural products, do not pose a health risk. This concept, without scientific basis... ends up offering serious risks to the health of less enlightened people⁴⁶.

Regarding the categorisation of plants, there are 18 different types⁴², including: Exterior-releasing plants (hot and cold); Fire-draining plants (cold); Purgatives; Water-regulating and dampness-draining plants; Wind-and-dampness-dispelling plants; Phlegm-transforming and cough-stopping plants; Aromatic dampness-transforming plants; Food stagnation-relieving plants; *Qi*-regulating plants; *Xue*-regulating plants; Interior-warming

and cold-expelling plants; Tonic plants; Astringent/stabilising substances; Heart-nourishing and spirit-calming plants; Orifice-opening aromatic substances; Wind-extinguishing and tremor-stopping substances; Parasite-expelling plants; and External application substances.

3.3. Phytotherapy in the treatment of low back pain according to TCM

Phytotherapy treats both manifestations and causes, using formulas consisting of a variable number of plants based on their energetic characteristics. These preparations restore the patient's balance. However, it is important to underline that these must be prepared by a professional, especially since some herbs are prohibited during pregnancy as they may contribute to miscarriage^{47,48}.

Furthermore, in phytotherapeutic prescription, it is necessary to consider the individual characteristics of the patient (e.g., weight and age) so that the effects of the active compounds are appropriate. A complete anamnesis is crucial⁴⁹. These factors are essential from the perspective of the compound's bioaccessibility; if the dose is too low, bioavailability may be significantly reduced, compromising benefits, while an excess can be harmful⁴⁹.

Regarding lumbar pain, it may arise due to Kidney *Yang* deficiency, affecting the warming and nutrition of this region; phytotherapy can be used to tonify Kidney *Yang* and strengthen the body's energy⁹. Jahromi *et al.*⁵⁰ explain that the formula *Du Huo Ji Sheng Tang* is widely used to warm the meridians, tonify Kidney *Yang*, and nourish *Xue*, showing efficacy in treating chronic LBP.

LBP can also arise due to *Qi* and *Xue* stagnation, which causes intense and localised pain; treatment serves to move *Qi* and *Xue*, relieving pain and restoring circulation in the meridians⁵¹. To treat this condition, *Yan Hu Suo* (*Corydalis*) and *Chuan Xiong* (*Ligusticum*) can be used, herbs with analgesic properties that promote blood circulation⁹.

Additionally, the invasion of cold and dampness, which can block the flow of *Qi* and *Xue* in the meridians of the lumbar region, can cause acute pain, stiffness, and a feeling of heaviness⁵². The formula *Juan Bi Tang* can be used to disperse cold and dampness, stimulating *Qi* circulation and relieving pain⁵⁰.

4. Phytotherapy vs. Pharmacology for the Treatment of Low Back Pain

Regarding treatment by phytotherapy, the article by Majumdar *et al.*⁵³ stands out, finding that the combination of *Boswellia serrata* and *Curcuma longa* significantly reduced pain, disability, and inflammatory biomarkers, decreasing the need for analgesics. These findings confirm the anti-inflammatory and analgesic potential of medicinal plants, as mentioned by Pinela⁹.

The study by Gupta *et al.*⁵⁴ reinforces the idea of Pinela⁹, showing that the *Rhuleave-K* formula provided rapid and substantial relief from postural lumbar pain, being safe and effective in the short term.

Similarly, Pham *et al.*⁵⁵ demonstrated that the VH supplement, together with electroacupuncture, improved pain, mobility, and function, showing superior results compared to acupuncture alone. These results align with the TCM approach, which favours combined and integrated therapies. Sung *et al.*⁵⁶ corroborate this perspective by showing that the use of *Palmijihwang-hwan* associated with acupuncture not only decreases pain and improves function but also presents an additional advantage in terms of cost-effectiveness.

Regarding pharmacological treatment, the results of the study by Saragiotto *et al.*⁵⁷ reveal that paracetamol is not superior to placebo in non-specific acute LBP, questioning its use as a first line of treatment. Previously, Brazil *et al.*⁷ had mentioned that the efficacy of some drugs is debatable.

Focusing on the use of systemic corticosteroids, Chou *et al.*⁵⁸ indicate that these have limited short-term benefit only for radicular pain, but are not effective for non-radicular pain or spinal stenosis. Khankhel *et al.*⁵⁹ found that oral ibuprofen is more effective than

topical diclofenac, but the combination of the two adds no benefit, demonstrating that pharmacological choice must be judicious and individualised.

In Wertli *et al.*⁶⁰, it is noted that NSAIDs are the class with the best results in LBP; however, they relieve but do not "remove" the pain, and prolonged use carries risks.

Regarding the use of antidepressants in the treatment of LBP, the study by Ferraro *et al.*⁶¹ concludes that pain improvement is modest and presents higher rates of adverse effects, requiring caution in their use.

Finally, the results obtained by McKenzie *et al.*⁶² reinforce the variety of results in this second theme, showing a lack of consensus among clinical guidelines, especially regarding pharmacological approaches. This reinforces the uncertainty and the need for complementary alternatives such as phytotherapy and acupuncture.

Therefore, and following the initial idea that LBP is highly prevalent and disabling^{1,3}. It is possible to see from the included studies that various therapeutic approaches relieve pain and improve quality of life and function^{53,55-57}. Conventional treatment includes drugs and physiotherapy, but surgery is an exception^{7,8}. Studies focusing on pharmacological treatment⁵⁷⁻⁶¹ confirm that, although exclusively used, they present limited efficacy or risks of adverse effects. Conversely, studies focused on phytotherapy⁵³⁻⁵⁶ present consistent results in terms of pain reduction, functional improvement, and safety, validating the perspective that phytotherapy can be a relevant complementary alternative in the treatment of LBP.

5. Conclusion

This review confirms that LBP is a complex global challenge requiring more than just standard "one-size-fits-all" treatments. While conventional drugs like NSAIDs are the norm, their limited efficacy in some cases and the risk of side effects highlight a clear need for better alternatives.

Phytotherapy, based on TCM, offers a scientifically viable solution. Studies show that herbal formulas (like *Du Huo Ji Sheng Tang*) provide significant pain relief and functional recovery with fewer risks. Furthermore, combining these herbs with acupuncture often proves more effective and cost-efficient than medication alone.

In summary, integrating phytotherapy into a multidisciplinary approach allows for more personalised care. While more clinical trials are needed to refine dosages, the current evidence strongly supports using these natural alternatives to improve patient quality of life and reduce the global burden of chronic pain.

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References

1. Pires RAM, Dumas FVL. Lombalgia: revisão de conceitos e métodos de tratamentos. *Universitas: Ciências da Saúde* (encerrada). 2008;6(2):159-68.
2. de Abreu MM. Abordagem clínica nas lombalgias: uma revisão narrativa. *Medicina, Ciência e Arte*. 2023;2(1):42-60.
3. Serranheira F, Mafalda S-U, Heranz F, Sacadura-Leite E, Kovacs F, Sousa-Uva A. Lombalgias e trabalho: serão importantes as exigências físicas do trabalho? *Low-Back Pain (LBP) and Work: how important are the physical demands?*
4. Kislaya I, Neto M. Caracterização sociodemográfica da prevalência da dor lombar crónica autorreportada na população residente em Portugal através do Inquérito Nacional de Saúde 2014. 2017.
5. Mourcel P-L. Avaliação da prevalência de dor lombar em jovens adultos e avaliação da resistência dos flexores e extensores do tronco em indivíduos com e sem história de dor lombar não específica: [sn]; 2017.
6. Santos FLMD, Silva KFD, Alencar Id. A prevalência de lombalgia em universitários: revisão de literatura. *Research, Society and Development*. 2021;10(13):e353101321347. doi: <https://doi.org/10.33448/rsd-v10i13.21347>
7. Brazil A, Ximenes AC, Radu AS, Fernandes A, Appel C, Maçaneiro C, et al. Diagnóstico e tratamento das lombalgias e lombociatalgias. *Revista brasileira de reumatologia*. 2004;44:419-25.
8. Junior PCN. Comparação dos tratamentos conservador, cirúrgico e através da mobilização neural no tratamento da hérnia de disco lombar. *Fisioterapia Brasil*. 2012;13(2):148-54.
9. Pinela MJPR. Eficácia da Medicina Tradicional Chinesa no tratamento da Lombalgia 2024.
10. Gomes BJF. Impacto da dor lombar na produtividade laboral: Universidade de Coimbra (Portugal); 2011.
11. de Abreu Coimbra L. Estudo da relação entre a lombalgia, a qualidade de vida, a satisfação com a vida e o desempenho cognitivo em adultos: Universidade Autônoma de Lisboa (Portugal); 2023.
12. Izzo R, Popolizio T, D'Aprile P, Muto M. Spinal pain. *Eur J Radiol*. 2015;84(5):746-56. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejrad.2015.01.018>
13. DeSai C, Reddy V, Agarwal A. *Anatomy, back, vertebral column*. 2018.
14. Kumar V, Kumar M. Common Types of Degenerative Spinal Disorders: An Overview. *A Comprehensive Guide to Degenerative Spine Disorders*. 2025:37-61.
15. Twain M. *Musculoskeletal Pathologies, Disorders, and Injuries*. *Mosby's Pathology for Massage Professionals-E-Book: Mosby's Pathology for Massage Professionals-E-Book*. 2021;114.
16. Imamura ST, Kaziyama HHS, Imamura M. Lombalgia. *Revista de Medicina*. 2001;80(spe2):375-90. doi: <https://doi.org/10.11606/issn.1679-9836.v80ispe2p375-390>
17. Gomes A. opióides e Lombalgia. *Lombalgias-1*. 2006.
18. Guerreiro VM. Abordagem da lombalgia em adultos nos cuidados de saúde primários: Universidade de Coimbra (Portugal); 2016.
19. Lopes GLT. *Lombalgia Crónica: Estratégia Conjunta Entre Medicina Geral e Familiar e Medicina Física e Reabilitação: Universidade de Coimbra (Portugal)*; 2022.
20. Baraúna M, Vinícius M, Mendes B, Barbosa G, Sanchez H, Ângelo R, et al. Estudo correlacional entre lombalgia e concavidade lombar em universitários *Correlational study between low back pain and lumbar lordosis in students* Artigo original. 2006.
21. Chou R, Qaseem A, Snow V, Casey D, Cross JT, Jr., Shekelle P, et al. Diagnosis and treatment of low back pain: a joint clinical practice guideline from the American College of Physicians and the American Pain Society. *Ann Intern Med*. 2007;147(7):478-91. doi: <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-147-7-200710020-00006>
22. Summaries for patients. Diagnosis and treatment of low back pain: recommendations from the American College of Physicians/American Pain Society. *Ann Intern Med*. 2007;147(7):I45. doi: <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-147-7-200710020-00025>

23. Oliveira CB, Maher CG, Pinto RZ, Traeger AC, Lin CC, Chenot JF, et al. Clinical practice guidelines for the management of non-specific low back pain in primary care: an updated overview. *Eur Spine J.* 2018;27(11):2791-803. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00586-018-5673-2>
24. Qaseem A, Wilt TJ, McLean RM, Forciea MA, Clinical Guidelines Committee of the American College of P, Denberg TD, et al. Noninvasive Treatments for Acute, Subacute, and Chronic Low Back Pain: A Clinical Practice Guideline From the American College of Physicians. *Ann Intern Med.* 2017;166(7):514-30. doi: <https://doi.org/10.7326/M16-2367>
25. Delitto A, George SZ, Van Dillen L, Whitman JM, Sowa G, Shekelle P, et al. Low back pain. *J Orthop Sports Phys Ther.* 2012;42(4):A1-57. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2519/jospt.2012.42.4.A1>
26. Borenstein D. Mechanical low back pain--a rheumatologist's view. *Nat Rev Rheumatol.* 2013;9(11):643-53. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrrheum.2013.133>
27. Strand LI, Kvale A, Raheim M, Ljunggren AE. Do Norwegian manual therapists provide management for patients with acute low back pain in accordance with clinical guidelines? *Man Ther.* 2005;10(1):38-43. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.math.2004.07.003>
28. Sharif S, Jazaib Ali MY, Kirazli Y, Vlok I, Zygourakis C, Zileli M. Acute back pain: The role of medication, physical medicine and rehabilitation: WFNS spine committee recommendations. *World Neurosurg X.* 2024;23:100273. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wnsx.2024.100273>
29. Doria M, Careddu D, Iorio R, Verrotti A, Chiappini E, Barbero GM, et al. Paracetamol and Ibuprofen in the Treatment of Fever and Acute Mild-Moderate Pain in Children: Italian Experts' Consensus Statements. *Children (Basel).* 2021;8(10). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/children8100873>
30. Klotz U. Paracetamol (acetaminophen) - a popular and widely used nonopioid analgesic. *Arzneimittelforschung.* 2012;62(8):355-9. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0032-1321785>
31. Abuse NIOD. Prescription opioids drugfacts. 2021.
32. Jamison RN, Mao J, editors. Opioid analgesics. *Mayo Clinic Proceedings*; 2015: Elsevier.
33. Paul AK, Smith CM, Rahmatullah M, Nissapatorn V, Wilairatana P, Spetea M, et al. Opioid Analgesia and Opioid-Induced Adverse Effects: A Review. *Pharmaceuticals (Basel).* 2021;14(11):1091. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph14111091>
34. Hall H, McIntosh G. Low back pain (chronic). *BMJ Clin Evid.* 2008;2008.
35. de Souza PM, Livramento RA, verçoza Lima I, Cunha WP. Intervenções Fisioterapêuticas na Dor Lombar Crônica: Uma Revisão de Literatura. *Brazilian Journal of Implantology and Health Sciences.* 2023;5(5):3379-95.
36. Santana AN, Sampaio IdC, Reis LAd. Eficácia da terapia manual na melhora da dor e amplitude de movimento em pacientes com lombalgia. *Research, Society and Development.* 2025;14(2):e6314248234. doi: <https://doi.org/10.33448/rsd-v14i2.48234>
37. Lopes B. Tratamento farmacológico na lombalgia. In: Antunes F, editor. *Tópicos em destaque na dor Lombalgia – tratamento não invasivo.* Lisboa: Permanyer; 2022. p. 1-14.
38. da Silva AR. *Fundamentos da Medicina Tradicional Chinesa.* 1997.
39. Matos LC, Machado JP, Monteiro FJ, Greten HJ. Understanding Traditional Chinese Medicine Therapeutics: An Overview of the Basics and Clinical Applications. *Healthcare (Basel, Switzerland).* 2021;9(3). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9030257>
40. Maciocia G. *The Foundations of Chinese Medicine: A Comprehensive Text for Acupuncturists and Herbalists:* Elsevier Churchill Livingstone; 2005. 9780443074899.
41. Maciocia G. *Diagnosis in Chinese Medicine: A Comprehensive Guide:* Elsevier; 2018. 9780702044144.
42. Oliveira A. *Fitoterapia chinesa.* Porto: Faculdade de Ciências da Saúde da Universidade Fernando Pessoa; 2016.
43. Bensky D, Clavey S, Stöger E. *Chinese Herbal Medicine: Materia Medica:* Eastland Press; 2004. 9780939616428.
44. Jingshen *Acupuncture and Chinese Medicine.* Chinese Herbal Medicine 2024 [Available from: <https://chinesemedicinesalon.blogspot.com/search?q=vitamin+D>].
45. INCCOR Academy. *Fitoterapia: origem e importância* nd. [Available from: <https://inccor.com.br/fitoterapia-origem-e-importancia/>].

46. Fontana C, Pedron A, Brezolun M. Protocolo de prescrição de fitoterápicos: Secretaria Municipal de Saúde; 2022 [Available from: <https://www.franciscobeltrao.pr.gov.br/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/PROTOCOLODE-FITOTERAPICOS-OK.pdf>].
47. Isenberg BC. Medicinal plants in obstetrics and gynaecology: how plants can support a woman in conceiving, being pregnant and giving birth, but also in preventing conception and aborting/vorgelegt von Bettina Cornelia Isenberg. 2021.
48. Bernstein N, Akram M, Yaniv-Bachrach Z, Daniyal M. Is it safe to consume traditional medicinal plants during pregnancy? *Phytotherapy research*. 2021;35(4):1908-24.
49. Piovesan F, Simão L, Silva T. Biodisponibilidade. In: Vitorello C, editor. *Plantas medicinais e fitoterapia: tradição e ciência*: Fealq; 2023. p. 55-68.
50. Jahromi B, Pirvulescu I, Candido KD, Knezevic NN. Herbal Medicine for Pain Management: Efficacy and Drug Interactions. *Pharmaceutics* [Internet]. 2021; 13(2):[251 p.]. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics13020251>
51. Ross J. *Combinações dos pontos de acupuntura: a chave para o êxito clínico*. São Paulo: Roca. 2003.
52. Yuan QL, Guo TM, Liu L, Sun F, Zhang YG. Traditional Chinese medicine for neck pain and low back pain: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *PloS one*. 2015;10(2):e0117146. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0117146>
53. Majumdar A, Prasad M, Gandavarapu SR, Reddy KSK, Sureja V, Kheni D, et al. Efficacy and safety evaluation of *Boswellia serrata* and *Curcuma longa* extract combination in the management of chronic lower back pain: A randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled clinical study. *Explore (NY)*. 2025;21(1):103099. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.explore.2024.103099>
54. Gupta A, Agarwal A. The effect of turmeric-*Boswellia* formulation (Rhuleave-K) in posture-related low back soreness and discomfort: A randomized double blinded placebo controlled trial. *J Back Musculoskelet Rehabil*. 2025;38(3):494-505. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/10538127241296343>
55. Pham PT, Hoang QT, Trinh LV, Nguyen AK, Han B, Hoang BX. Efficacy and Safety of Vuong Hoat Natural Health Supplement in Managing Low Back Pain: A Randomized Clinical Trial. *J Med Food*. 2025;28(1):87-95. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1089/jmf.2023.0284>
56. Sung WS, Jeon SR, Hong YJ, Kim TH, Shin S, Lee HJ, et al. Efficacy, safety, and cost-effectiveness analysis of adjuvant herbal medicine treatment, Palmijihwang-hwan, for chronic low back pain: a study protocol for randomized, controlled, assessor-blinded, multicenter clinical trial. *Trials*. 2019;20(1):778. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-019-3776-7>
57. Saragiotto BT, Machado GC, Ferreira ML, Pinheiro MB, Abdel Shaheed C, Maher CG. Paracetamol for low back pain. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2016;2016(6):CD012230. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD012230>
58. Chou R, Pinto RZ, Fu R, Lowe RA, Henschke N, McAuley JH, et al. Systemic corticosteroids for radicular and non-radicular low back pain. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2022;10(10):CD012450. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD012450.pub2>
59. Khankhel N, Friedman BW, Baer J, Lopez L, Feliciano C, Lee S, et al. Topical Diclofenac Versus Oral Ibuprofen Versus Diclofenac + Ibuprofen for Emergency Department Patients With Acute Low Back Pain: A Randomized Study. *Ann Emerg Med*. 2024;83(6):542-51. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annemergmed.2024.01.037>
60. Wertli MM, Steurer J. [Pain medications for acute and chronic low back pain]. *Internist (Berl)*. 2018;59(11):1214-23. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00108-018-0475-5>
61. Ferraro MC, Bagg MK, Wewege MA, Cashin AG, Leake HB, Rizzo RRN, et al. Efficacy, acceptability, and safety of antidepressants for low back pain: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Syst Rev*. 2021;10(1):62. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-021-01599-4>
62. McKenzie BJ, Haas R, Ferreira GE, Gorelik A, Cyril S, Han JX, et al. Agreement between high-quality clinical practice guidelines in their treatment recommendations for low back pain: a systematic review. *Spine J*. 2025;25(12):2587-604. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spinee.2025.07.015>